

**THE USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION
AS AN OPPORTUNITY TO INCREASE THE COMPETITIVENESS
OF UNIVERSITIES IN THE EUROPEAN SPACE**

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ABSTRACT. In the modern world, the education process occurs not only through special social institutions, but also through self-education, i.e. acquisition of skills and knowledge in a certain field by independent forces. Education is considered to be a specific human activity, which is aimed at acquiring systematic views, skills and ideas in a particular area. The strategic mission of the modern education system is to promote ideas, projects and innovations that contribute to the effective modernization of the school. The reference point in this case will be the rich heritage of culture, which for centuries has been created by humanity and needs not only to be used, but most often to discover.

Science, new technologies and developments - everything that contributes to the development of processes in education must be introduced into school reality. This does not mean that continuous experimentation will replace established teaching methods. But excessive conservatism and preservation of the established tradition in teaching a new generation will not make the process perfect.

Key words: *the education process, new technologies, teaching methods.*

Introduction. Socio-economic changes in the world dictate a different approach in the upbringing and education of a new generation. The processes are so fast that we have to catch up, and not get ahead of events, and it is the school that is an indicator of the development of our society: a new generation is born in it, and therefore processes of renewal should occur in the school, affecting all areas of the development of society. In this case, we mean not only secondary schools, but also colleges, as well as universities, whose information reaches foreign media faster than domestic ones.

In today's Digital Age, the use of Educational technology provides numerous advantages for a wide range of settings, namely primary and secondary education, higher education, STEM, corporates and for the general public. Examples are improved personalized learning, improved engagement in classes, cost savings and more. The rapid spread of COVID-19 around the world has caused increasing attention to Educational technology as a substitute for traditional, face-to-face classes. In spite of the emerging issues regarding Educational technology, such as transparency regarding data, its use must be promoted to obtain digital competencies, to tackle complex challenges and to enhance learning and performance.

Research Methodology. The current study is based on an analysis of existing rules, strategic documents and an analysis of the development of the education system educational system all over the world and especially in European countries. The study includes a survey of opinions, ratings and analyzes of representatives from various categories of organizations in expert and managerial positions.

To create this document, a lot of documentation was used, based on the main sources of information about the education and science system at the international level, representing in a

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logical and critical way the approaches of various authors in relation to: definition, role and importance, principles, determinants and achievements in the field of study.

Findings. Modern educational technology refers to the use of technology in order to facilitate learning and performance. Educational technology is a wide field in the sense that any kind of hardware or software that enhances learning or instruction is considered to be Educational technology. Apart from learning and performance, Educational technology facilitates communication as well as organizing and exchanging knowledge. Instruction with Educational technology can exceed traditional instruction without Educational technology by providing a wide range of capabilities that stimulate engaging, efficient and effective learning.

For teachers and instructors, Educational technology creates a wide opportunity to use different teaching methods that could not have been done before, which can enrich students and trainees. Examples of educational technologies are: *computer aided learning, cloud computing, audiovisual aids, mobile and smart technologies, virtual and augmented reality, immersive environments, gamification and artificial intelligence* (European Commission, 2019).

The use of Educational technologies in education or training has numerous advantages:

- **Learning becomes more personal and diverse.** Students are able to learn at their own pace.

- **It enables students to train in simulated environments close to reality**, which would be impossible or unsafe without the use of educational technologies.

- **It enables remote learning**, which makes the continuation of education possible during the current Covid-19 pandemic.

- **Students can access the online learning materials** at any time.

- **It saves costs** and improves the current setups of schools and training rooms.

- **It makes learning more dynamic**, engageable and exciting. It helps for students who don't raise their hand in class or are scared to ask questions.

- Because of the rapid technological advance in today's digital age, **it is crucial to obtain digital skills and competencies.**

- Thanks to educational technologies research, new insights, developments and **improvements can be made regarding to the desired outcomes** of educational technologies.

In spite of these advantages, some concerns arise considering Educational technologies:

- Students who learn solely online might suffer from their lack of socializing and developing social skills coming from interactions with others. In order to tackle this concern, a healthy combination of on-campus teaching and online learning should be adopted (blended learning). However, this remains a general issue during the Covid19 pandemic.

- By using Educational technologies, student data is collected to promote personalized learning and improvement. Trainers and Educational technologies providers have to be transparent in which data they collect and how data can be used. Many websites collect data without explicit user permission. Selling data without permission is unethical, but often remains a grey area.

- It is crucial to ensure that the used Educational technologies tools are qualitatively in line with the learning objectives. Educational institutions and companies must create a clear ICT vision and make informed decisions. Using Educational technologies should not be considered a goal itself, but rather an instrument to reach the learning objectives easier and faster.

- Lack of equal access to Educational technologies between developed and developing countries or between the well-to-do and the poor. In order for every person to benefit from Educational technologies, universal access and means is a necessity.

- In some cultures and generations, there are reluctant adopters of technology or have a different understanding of technology and its means during a lesson. Cultural differences may have a negative impact on student participation during online classes.

The Educational technologies sector is an expanding industry and is on the rise worldwide, as well as the demand for educational technologies. This is seen by the rapid growth of commercial Educational technologies companies as well as Educational technologies research all over the world. Educational technologies has become a major part of educational programs and trainings in institutions and companies worldwide (Magda A. J., et al, 2018).

There are two types of administration platforms in the higher education environment:

Fig. 1. Types of administration platforms in the higher education environment

The first type facilitates administration between students and their lectures. The second type facilitates administration only between students.

Examples of used platforms for centralization and structuring of information as well as digital evaluation and feedback are *Blackboard, Moodle, Canvas, Google Classroom, D2L's Brightspace and Chamilo*.

The second type facilitates collaboration and assignment or project performance between students. The functionalities of this category are centralization and structuring of information, digital communication and document sharing. Examples of these platforms are *Google Workspace, Dropbox, Miro, Microsoft Teams and Padlet*.

The huge demand for these apps and many other learning technologies revealed by the COVID-19 pandemic is forcing actors and startups to innovate, roll out and expand to supply their consumers who are bound to seek fast digital solutions. The pandemic has opened the eyes of the investor community to the education technology scene and its potential for significant growth in the coming years. VC investment in Educational technologies has increased tenfold since 2014, hitting a record level of 711 million USD. The European Educational technologies market has been becoming an increasingly attractive opportunity both for local and international investors over the past few years. This growth in funding originates from increased innovation and adoption as well as demand and supply:

Fig. 2. Educational technologies VC investments in Europe since 2014 (not including growth, private equity, grants and debt financing deals)

Source: Arno De Kepper, 2022

The investigation, regarding VC investments in the Educational technologies scene shows the UK as the leader of the European Educational technologies sector and the potential of the other European countries, as seen in figure 2. For each year, the countries are ranked according to the number of total deals funded. The total value of all deals are provided per country as well. The UK maintains a dominant position in the European Educational technologies scene since 2016, apart from 2018. In 2020, the UK comprised ± 40% of the total deals funded and took ± 30% of the value of all deals. However, it registered a decline in absolute numbers in comparison to 2019.

Beyond Europe, the pandemic has resulted in disruption to learning on an unseen global scale, with the rapid uptake of Educational technologies supporting education continuity at all levels:

Fig. 3. Regional share of Global Educational technologies
Source: HolonIQ, 2021

VC investment in Educational technologies has witnessed a corresponding increase, with the market of China as the global leader, surpassing the share of VC investments in the American and European markets. Simultaneously, India has risen to become the third Educational technologies powerhouse, after China and the USA. Despite VC investments being a part of the total amount of investments, this research provides an overview of the Educational technologies powerhouses in Europe and the rest of the world.

The main tasks of education in the current period of development of the Moldovan state include improving the quality of education, creating social and pedagogical programs for youth development as a key condition for increasing social mobility of a person and changing the socio-psychological atmosphere in society. Inside the system of domestic education, at present, the prerequisites have formed for the transition to new models of educational policy.

An important role in this process is played by science as an innovative reserve for the development of the education system, including education management systems. Of particular importance is the organization and full funding of the scientific support of the state education development strategy.

Domestic science should solve the problems of implementing a program of retraining and advanced training of teachers, provide a real basis for the fundamentalization of teacher training, the development of motivation of teaching staff.

Sociological studies (Education-2020) have shown the importance of solving such problems as:

- providing material support to teachers,
- modernizing the material and technical base of an educational institution,
- raising the level of teachers' qualifications,

- improving the methodological support of the pedagogical process,
- developing scientific research,
- updating educational materials.

Important changes are currently taking place in the education system: the philosophy of open education is being phased in, which will largely be based on distance learning technologies, external studies, etc.

These technologies and types of training are characterized by reduced interactivity, low regulation of the student's actions and require additional efforts for persistent and systematic studies. The use of these technologies and types of training will be facilitated by creative, creative pedagogy. Unlike traditional, it relies on an independent search for ways to solve the problem. Creative pedagogy teaches students to learn creatively, to become creators of themselves and creators of their future. After all, the main capital of the present and future will not be technology, but intelligence and creative thinking.

Therefore, the main goal of the educational system of the country is formulated very specifically. This is providing opportunities for the formation of an individual educational route, unlocking the creative potential of a person with the goal of the most complete self-realization, achieving the highest quality of educational standards and the level of professional training.

In this case, the main role is given to educational institutions, for which it is important to realize the significance and advantages of a creative approach, when the development of the imagination, determination, individuality of students will motivate them to educational activities. It is interesting that at the same time creativity and learning outcomes are not opposed, but are considered as two sides of the same coin - creativity is perceived as a way to achieve the next level in the development of knowledge.

Conclusions

The competition of various educational systems has become a key element of global competition, requiring constant updating of technologies, accelerated development of innovations, quick adaptation to the demands and requirements of a dynamically changing world. At the same time, the possibility of obtaining a quality education continues to be one of the most important life values of citizens, a decisive factor in social justice and political stability.

Increasing the level of knowledge, competence and skills to generate the new depends directly on the lifelong education and training system, which directly supports the creation of a new profile of the individual engaged in the knowledge society, society characterized by lifelong learning. These challenges lead to major changes at the micro and macroeconomic level, ensuring the transition to the knowledge society in which added value and increased competitiveness are correlated with the degree of knowledge and the ability to generate the new.

The development of the education system should be based on such principles of project activity as openness of education to external needs, application of project methods, competitive identification and support of leaders who successfully implement new approaches in practice, targeting of resource support tools and the integrated nature of decisions made.

Updating organizational and economic mechanisms at all levels of the education system will ensure its compliance with promising trends in economic development and social needs, increase the practical orientation of the industry, its investment attractiveness.

The ability to innovate, as well as the willingness to cooperate, to interconnect efficient and competitive activities in the field of knowledge are skills that are acquired through education, resulting in creative people, able to formulate hypotheses, able to communicate and cooperate in the effort to achieve common goals.

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